

MULTIFUNCTIONAL TRANSPARENT EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES AS ENCAPSULATING MATERIALS FOR LED DEVICES

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SUMMARY

Our recent progress in multifunctional transparent epoxy nanocomposites has been briefly reviewed. The UV-light shielding efficiency was enhanced by introduction of ZnO and SiO₂/TiO₂ nanoparticles. A strategy for facile synthesis of highly transparent polymer nanocomposites was proposed and transparent and light emitting epoxy nanocomposites were successfully prepared.

Keywords: transparent epoxy, photoluminescence, transmittance, nanocomposites

1. INTRODUCTION

Incandescent bulbs and halogen lamps have been widely used for general lighting in houses and offices etc but they are relatively high-energy consumptive, lowly reliable and short-lived. Therefore, solid state lighting emitting diodes (LEDs) have drawn great attention for general illumination because LEDs have advantages over incandescent and halogen lamps in terms of power efficiency, reliability and lifetime etc [1,2]. In standard solid state lighting emitting diode (LED) technology, transparent epoxy resins due to their high transparency, high-glass transition temperature, low-water absorption and standard process ability are most frequently employed as packaging materials for LED devices [3-9]. In practical applications, the whole LED lamp is encapsulated with a transparent epoxy resin, as illustrated in Figure 1a [7]. Nonetheless, the severe yellowing of epoxy encapsulant would occur due to junction heat and short-wavelength emission [7,9]. This would significantly shorten the lifetime of LEDs. Since the mixture of phosphors with epoxy encapsulant is close to the die for usual LED lamps, it was suggested that the structure of LEDs could be designed with the phosphor layer far away from the die to lower the degradation of epoxy [7-9]. However, this improvement in lowering epoxy degradation is very limited since the distance between the phosphor layer and the die is restricted by the LED structure.

The present paper briefly reviews our recent research work on multifunctional transparent epoxy nanocomposites as encapsulating materials for the ultraviolet LED lamps as shown in Figure 1b [10,11]. Notable inorganic nanoparticles including ZnO, SiO₂ and TiO₂ as well as their composite nanoparticles with very fine sizes are uniformly dispersed in the transparent epoxy matrix to prepare nanocomposite encapsulating materials for the LED lamps. At first, the enhancement of UV-light shielding efficiency was reported by introducing ZnO and SiO₂/TiO₂ nanoparticles into

epoxy resins to improve the lifetime of LED lamps [3,4]. Since the visible-light transmittance is rapidly reduced as the nanoparticle content increases in the epoxy nanocomposites, it is thus of importance to maintain the high transmittance of transparent polymer matrices. Thus, facile synthesis of highly transparent polymer nanocomposites was then reported by introduction of core-shell structured nanoparticles into transparent polymer matrices [12]. On the other hand, transparent polymer resins can not emit visible light while ZnO quantum dots etc and their nanocomposite particles can emit visible light under excitation of UV light. Therefore, transparent and light emitting epoxy nanocomposites were prepared by introducing quantum dots and their nanocomposite particles into the epoxy matrix as encapsulating for LED lamps [10,11,13].

Figure 1. Schematic of (a) the standard 5 mm LED [7] and (b) the new LED structure [10,11].

2. PHOTO-STABILIZATION PROPERTIES

Figure 2 exhibits transmission electron microscopy (TEM) micrographs of the ZnO and core-shell structured SiO₂-TiO₂ (S-T) nanoparticles [4]. It can be seen from Figure 2a that most of the individual ZnO particles are near spherical in shape with an average particle size of about 26.7 nm. TEM picture of S-T nanoparticles (with 36.5wt% titania) after annealing at 600oC for 2h is exhibited in Figure 2b. These S-T particles are near spherical in shape with an average particle size of about 69 nm. The titania has been uniformly coated on the surface of silica core since titania-coated silica particles became bigger and rougher compared to pure silica particles. Figure 2c exhibits that core-shell-shell structured SiO₂-TiO₂-SiO₂ (S-T-S) nanoparticles are also near spherical in shape. The dark color in the TEM micrographs was caused by overlapping of S-T-S nanoparticles.

Transparent ZnO/epoxy nanocomposites were prepared from transparent epoxy (EP-400) and ZnO nano-particles via in-situ polymerization. The UV-VIS transmittance spectra of epoxy and nanocomposites (0.07 wt%) are shown in Figure 3a [3]. As the calcination temperature increases, the transmittance of UV light generally decreases.

Though the samples calcined at 400oC or above (Z6-Z8) exhibit almost perfect UV light shielding efficiency (see Figure 3a), their transparencies are quite poor (see Figure 4 [3]). However, it can be seen from Figure 3a that the nanocomposite containing Z5 nano-particles calcined at 350 oC shows not only high UV light shielding (~96% at 320 nm and ~91% at 370 nm) but also high visible light transparency (see Figure 4).

Since only an extremely low content (0.07 wt%) of ZnO nano-particles was added to the transparent epoxy resin, the physical and mechanical properties were not changed, thus the processability of the nanocomposite-packaging material would not change. Indeed, easy processing of these transparent ZnO/epoxy nanocomposites has been confirmed in practical encapsulation of UV-WLED. Figure 5 shows the standard UV-WLED lamps encapsulated with pure transparent epoxy resin (a) and ZnO/epoxy nanocomposite resin (b) [3]. Except the processability, the appearances of the two lamps are also the same.

Figure 2. TEM photographs of (a) UV-filter ZnO, (b) S-T (b) and (c) S-T-S nanoparticles [4].

The photo-stabilization properties of pure transparent epoxy and various inorganic UV-filter/epoxy nanocomposites as UV-LED encapsulating materials were studied for the life test with the 50% reduction in the light output intensity of LED. The results of lifetime test were shown in Figure 6 [4]. It can be seen that the relative light output of UV-LED lamps decreases rapidly during the initial period of about two hundred hours, and afterwards changes slowly. This phenomenon was consistent with the previous research results [7]. It was found that the intensity of pure transparent epoxy encapsulated UV-LED decreased more rapidly than other LED lamps encapsulated with

nanocomposites. Therefore, the inorganic UV-filter nanoparticles can effectively improve the photo-stability of encapsulation materials and hence prolong LED's lifetime. Compared with the pure epoxy encapsulated UV-LED, the lifetime of ZnO/epoxy, S-T/epoxy and S-T-S/epoxy nanocomposite encapsulated UV-LED lamps has been improved by 76%, 33% and 54%, respectively.

Figure 3. UV-vis spectra of epoxy matrix and ZnO/T-epoxy nanocomposites containing 0.07 wt% ZnO nanoparticles [3].

Figure 4. Transparency of ZnO/T-epoxy nanocomposite samples with 0.07 wt% ZnO nanoparticle prepared at different temperatures [3].

Figure 5. UV-WLED lamps encapsulated with (a) pure transparent epoxy, and (b) ZnO/T-epoxy nanocomposite with 0.07 wt% ZnO content (Z5) [3].

Figure 6. Comparison of the intensity of LED chips encapsulated with pure epoxy matrix and inorganic UV-filter/epoxy nanocomposites [4].

Figure 7. UV-LED lamps before and after lifetime testing. Lamp A, B and C were encapsulated with the ZnO/epoxy nanocomposite, the S-T/epoxy nanocomposite and the pure epoxy, respectively [4].

The appearances of UV-LED lamps before and after lifetime testing are shown in Figure 7 [4]. After lifetime testing, UV-LED encapsulating materials became yellow from colorless. It can be seen from Figure 7 that the UV-LED lamp encapsulated using pure epoxy resin after lifetime testing has been most severely degraded. Inversely, the ZnO/epoxy nanocomposite encapsulated UV-LED lamp has been most lightly degraded. The S-T/epoxy nanocomposite encapsulated UV-LED lamp showed the medium degree of degradation after lifetime testing. For inorganic UV-filter/epoxy nanocomposites, the inorganic UV-filter additives could decrease the degradation generated by UV-light. In fact, the UV-absorption property is a natural attribute of inorganic UV-filters according to the solid band theory.

3. TRANSMITTANCE

Figure 8a shows the transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image of pure silica [12]. The silica nanoparticles with uniform size were spherical with smooth surface and the average particle size was about 59 nm. TEM images of the core-shell structured S-T nanoparticles with a coating of 36.5 wt% titania on silica core before and after annealing were given in Figure 8b and 8c, respectively. TiO₂ was uniformly coated on the surface of the silica core since titania-coated silica particles became larger and rougher compared to pure silica particles and no isolated TiO₂ particles were observed. The dark color in Figure 8a-8c was caused by overlapping of nanoparticles. After annealing, the mean diameter of S-T nanoparticles was increased to about 69 nm. A typical core-shell structured S-T nanoparticle was shown in the inset of Figure 8c with a shell thickness of about 5 nm as a representative example. Figure 8d is scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of the core-shell structured S-T nanoparticles with a coating of 36.5 wt % titania on silica after annealing, confirming the uniformity and spherical shape of the S-T nanoparticles.

Figure 8. TEM images of (a) pure silica, (b) coated silica by titania with a weight percentage of 36.5 wt % before annealing, (c) TEM image and (d) SEM image of coated silica by 36.5 wt % titania after annealing for 2 h at 600°C [12].

UV-vis transmittance spectra of pure epoxy resin and S-T/epoxy nanocomposites with the 1 wt % filler content are shown in Figure 9a [12], where core-shell structured S-T nanoparticles have a relatively titania content of 0, 10, 20, 36.5, 45 and 60 wt%. It can be clearly seen that epoxy nanocomposites filled with pure silica nanoparticles is almost totally opaque within the whole UV-vis range. The transmittance of the S-T/epoxy nanocomposites varies as the shell content increases. The transmittance increases initially with increasing the relative shell content. And the visible light transmittance at 800 nm of the S-T/epoxy nanocomposites has the optimal value of 87 % when the titania coating content is 36.5 wt % as shown in Figure 9b [12]. Further increase in the weight percentage of titania shell leads to the decrease in the transmittance of S-T/epoxy nanocomposites. The effect of the titania shell content on

the corresponding transparency of the nanocomposites is exhibited in Figure 9c [12], which is consistent with Figure 9a and 9b. The highest transparency is observed at the 36.5 wt % titania shell content which corresponds to the case with a matching refractive index of the core-shell structured nanoparticles with the transparent epoxy matrix [12]. Core-shell structured S-T nanoparticles were considered as composites so that their refractive index (RI) can be calculated from the composite theory for the RI [14].

Figure 9. (a) UV-Vis transmittance spectra of the epoxy matrix and the S-T/epoxy nanocomposites, (b) transmittance of the S-T/epoxy nanocomposites at 800 nm, (c) optical photo of the nanocomposites as a function of the shell weight percentage [12].

4. LIGHT-EMITTING PROPERTIES

The average size of ZnO quantum dots (ZnO-QDs) was $3.1 \text{ nm} \pm 0.3 \text{ nm}$ from 50 measurements of the sizes of ZnO nanoparticles from the high resolution TEM images as shown in Figure 10 using the software SemAfore 4.0. The enlarged inset at the left-top corner of Figure 10 shows the lattice fringes belonging to wurtzite structure of ZnO nanocrystals. The fluorescence spectra of pure epoxy and transparent ZnO-QDs/epoxy nanocomposites under the excitation of 370 nm are shown in Figure 11. A weak emission peak at $\sim 442 \text{ nm}$ is observed for pure epoxy. The broad emission spectrum of ZnO-QDs/epoxy nanocomposites in the range of 400 nm to ca. 640 nm was observed with an emission peak at about 442 nm and the fluorescent intensity of nanocomposites increases with increasing the content of ZnO-QDs. The strong emission of ZnO-QDs/epoxy nanocomposites should arise from both the ZnO nanocrystals and the organic epoxy resin. Moreover, the peak of the epoxy nanocomposites has been blue shifted from the 509 nm for the ZnO-QDs to the 442 nm for the pure epoxy resin,

indicating that the epoxy matrix might play an important role in determining the peak location.

Figure 10. HRTEM image of the as-prepared ZnO nanocrystals [10].

The LED lamps were prepared by encapsulating LED chips with the pure epoxy and the ZnO-QDs/epoxy nanocomposite containing the 4 wt% ZnO-QDs. Optical photographs were taken using a digital Olympus camera for the encapsulated LED lamps as shown in the inset of Figure 11 [10]. The LED lamp encapsulated with the pure epoxy emits weak light because that the pure epoxy emits light with a weak emission peak at ~ 442 nm. The LED lamp encapsulated with the ZnO-QDs/epoxy nanocomposite emits white light and shows a much stronger luminescence intensity compared to that encapsulated using the pure epoxy resin. This is because the ZnO-QDs in the epoxy nanocomposite emit bright luminescence and the epoxy nanocomposite exhibits a broad photoluminescence emission spectrum. The encapsulated LED lamps in our lab are much larger in size than commercial ones so that the light intensity becomes weak at the top of the LED lamps.

Figure 11. Fluorescence emission spectra of pure epoxy and ZnO-QDs/epoxy nanocomposites excited at 370 nm. The inset shows the optical photographs of the UV-WLED lamps (370 nm) encapsulated with the pure transparent epoxy (left) and the ZnO-QDs/epoxy nanocomposite (right) containing the 4 wt% ZnO-QDs content [10].

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